

Information needs from policy makers translated in terms of functionality of HBM mixture information

Deliverable Report

D15.1

WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risk

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1 Authors and acknowledgements

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Since we guaranteed the interviewees confidentiality to allow them to 'speak their mind' even when personal views might be at odds with their official institutes' position, we cannot list participants by name, nor by institutes.

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2 Glossary

ACF - Advocacy Coalition Framework

EDC - endocrine disrupting substances

HJMP - Horizon2020 Joint Mixture Project cooperation

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3 Abstract/Summary

This document provides a first exploratory assessment of potential information needs from a governance perspective. It describes some background from the literature on risk governance, supplemented with first results of argumentation analyses on scientific controversy about (mixtures of) Endocrine Disrupting Compounds, as an example. It provides a first set of statements and questions taken from the current discourse on mixtures for use in future dialogues and surveys and provides first results of testing some of these questions in structured interviews with selected experts and policy makers. From this broader set of questions, six questions were piloted in semi-structured interviews, through telephone and face-to-face interviews.

From the interviews, the information needs from policy makers and experts appeared still rather diffuse and unarticulated. This limits our ability as yet to outline consequences for the desired functionality of HBM mixture information to serve policy development. Moreover, views on responsibilities and criteria to guide risk reduction strategies vary considerably, which warrants further exploration of views and mental models held by the stakeholders involved to further articulate information needs.

The authors consider the governance of health risks of mixtures from the perspective of a 'systemic risk' problem, which combines features of uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity. The governance of such uncertain, complex and ambiguous risk problems cannot be successfully performed solely through a technological-life sciences approach within multiple regulatory silos, but needs a broader discourse involving multiple stakeholders and civil society. The diversity of responses of the interviewees are in line with the systemic risk nature of mixtures.

Such a discourse can develop through the stakeholder consultations and dialogues that were initiated in the context of the Horizon2020 Joint Mixture Projects. The absence of clear contours for action perspectives and governance strategies for the management of mixture risks merit an impulse in strengthening the social and stakeholder dialogues on the complex issue of risk assessment and governance of chemical mixtures. It is therefore recommended to initiate a broad dialogue on information needs for mixture risk governance with stakeholders. Such an activity is as yet not planned. Any such exercise, within HBM4EU, should be done in conjunction with Pillar 1. Possibly, the earlier proposal (August 2018) on a Pan European Risk Perception Survey for an Internal Call mechanism, could be revisited as a starting point to initiate such dialogue

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4 Introduction and background

4.1 General background

Mixtures are a loosely defined term that may mean different things to different people, depending on their role and profession. To regulators it may mean combination of substances falling under their regulatory context and jurisdiction; to the public it may mean involuntary exposures possibly combined with an archetypical scare and suspicion that single-substance risk assessment are not telling the whole story, depending on their core beliefs and worldviews. To some producers, it may mean the composition of substances to make their product function as intended. To scientists it depends on their discipline and profession. Overall, the overlap in joint concepts and vocabulary is still limited, as depicted below.

Figure 1: Differences in concepts and vocabulary

The European Commission communication on “*The combination effects of chemicals – Chemical mixtures*” (Commission 2012) was published in response to a request from the European Parliament for the Commission to consider the extent to which the existing legislation “adequately addresses risks from exposure to multiple chemicals from different sources and pathways, and on this basis to consider appropriate modifications, guidelines and assessment methods”. In the communication mixtures are differentiated as follows:

- **Intentional mixtures:** these are manufactured formulated products that are marketed as such. The composition of such mixtures and the hazardous properties and classification of the constituents is known;
- **Mixtures originating from a single source:** also known as ‘unintentional mixtures’ these are the result of discharges to the environment during the production, transport, use or disposal of goods, often contain a mixture of chemical substances. The composition can either be known (for example an effluent) or it can be unknown; and
- **Mixtures of chemicals originating from multiple sources and through multiple pathways:** also known as “coincidental mixtures” these relate to multiple substances from multiple and varying sources. Their composition is unknown and can vary in both space and time.

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From an HBM perspective, a mixture is any combination of substances circulating simultaneously in the body originating from:

- simultaneous exposure to two or more substances from a single common source across single exposure routes;
- simultaneous exposure to two or more substances from multiple sources, exposure routes and pathways;
- repeated or chronic exposure to substances from multiple sources across multiple pathways; or
- any combination of the above.

Recently, EFSA issued a draft Guidance document on harmonised methodologies for human health, animal health and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals (EFSA Scientific Committee 2018). It distinguishes amongst other things a 'Whole Mixture approach' and a 'Component-based approach'. The Whole Mixture approach may work well for the evaluation of ecological risks, e.g. to assess the risk of all chemicals in a water body on the species in that water body. It is doubtful whether 'Whole Mixture' approaches in human health risk assessment can work, given our ignorance about the actual multi-route complex exposures in daily life. The draft Guidance document further proposes a tiered approach to exposure assessment, as in the diagram below:

	Occurrence data	Exposure estimate	Consumption data
Tier 0	Default values, permitted levels	Semi-quantitative point estimates	Default values, portion sizes
Tier 1	Modelled and experimental data	Deterministic	Food balance sheet food basket
Tier 2	Monitoring Surveys	Semi-probabilistic	Summary statistics
Tier 3	Individual co-occurrence data	Probabilistic	Individual data

Note: Occurrence and consumption data ranges from default values (tier 0) to individual co-occurrence data and individual data respectively (tier 3) and consequently exposure estimates range from semi-quantitative point estimates (tier 0) to probabilistic (tier 3). Occurrence and consumption tiers do not necessarily match.

Figure 4: Examples of tiers in exposure assessments

The ambition of HBM4EU WP15 is to contribute to tier 3 and to provide data on individual co-occurrence data to generate probabilistic exposure information for use in risk assessments.

This document draws on prior work from the literature of risk governance, on argumentation analyses, on discourse and discussions from multiple contacts within the context of the Horizon Joint Mixture projects. Building on this and on earlier work, a set of statements and questions was developed for future use to delineate different views on possible action perspectives and governance toward mixture risks.

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4.2 Information needs

Since the term ‘information need’ is widely used, but hardly ever defined we therefore first delineate the term in this this general section. According to Wikipedia (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Information_needs, last consulted 9-11-2018), the concept of ‘information need’ was developed by Robert S. Taylor in 1962 (Taylor 1962). In Taylors view, information need has four levels:

- The conscious and unconscious need for information not existing in the remembered experience of the inquirer. In terms of the query range, this level might be called the “ideal question” — the question which would bring from the ideal system exactly what the inquirer, if he could state his need. It is the actual, but unexpressed, need for information
- The conscious mental description of an ill-defined question. In this level, the inquirer has a conscious information need in the mind and might talk to someone else in the field to get an answer.
- A researcher forms a rational statement of his question. This statement is a rational and unambiguous description of the inquirer’s doubts.
- The question as presented to the information system.

As witnessed from documents of the regulatory bodies and in the HJMP, the ‘ideal question’ remains implicit. For the governance of mixture risks, we might express the conscious mental description of an ill-defined question as:

“How can we effectively and efficiently manage the health risks associated with chemical mixtures in the European population in such a way that residual mixture risks are considered acceptable from a public health and personal health point of view, while maintaining to the degree possible the societal and personal benefits of the products that lead to the mixture exposures”. Effectively and efficiently would entail not only a ‘utilitarian’ perspective, but also an ‘egalitarian’ perspective, meaning that the optimal situation is not only at the population level, but also involves social justice elements, such that risk groups are also sufficiently protected.

From this, we can derive a number of ‘rational statements’ and the questions that are relevant to HBM4EU. While risk governance in itself is not a primary objective of HBM4EU, strengthening the science-policy interface clearly is. Risk governance, as will be explained below, is one of the approaches for policy development and risk management (in addition to top-down hierarchical regulation by authorities). As such it forms a key element in the science-policy interface, particularly for risk problems where there is substantial complexity and uncertainty as is the case in the risk assessment of mixtures. Thus, to avoid ‘type IV errors’ (Type IV error refers to situation where the answer may in itself be correct and for the right reasons, but the answer does not address the question of concern (Lebret 2015), i.e. what action perspective is most desirable for policy development to manage mixture health risks) from the science side, potential options for policy development need to be sufficiently well articulated for the science answers to be informative to serve the information needs

1. When typical HBM mixtures patterns are defined (e.g. as through activities within WP15.1) what would constitute an ‘acceptable risk’ for mixtures and how can this be operationalized (e.g. would this involve risk-benefit considerations, feasibility issues, social justive aspects, the application of additional mixture safety or assessment factors, etcetera)?

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2. What is the *level* of acceptable risk to society (regulators, experts, stakeholders, civil society) of the chemical manmade cocktail in the European population?
3. Is this acceptable risk level exceeded, given the mixtures observed from HBM data in the European population? Are there differences between areas in Europe and/or different population sub-groups?
4. What are the main drivers (main constituents driving the mixture risk) and sources of unacceptable mixtures risk level?
5. What are the action perspectives to reduce an unacceptable mixtures risk level?

Follow up questions, more pertaining to the actual management of risks (and thus not in the core of the remit of HBM4EU) would be:

- Which actors are involved in the risk reduction and how?
- What is the optimal mix of actions to reduce the risk effectively and efficiently?
- Does the current regulatory system support the implementation of such sets of optimal risk reduction actions?

In the structure of Taylor, this set of questions can then be presented to the HBM4EU and wider information systems.

4.3 Mixtures as a systemic risk problem

In the discussion of the Horizon2020 Joint Mixture Projects (HJMP), mixture risks were considered as a ‘systemic risk’ problem. Systemic risks in the context of environmental health are complex risks to health embedded in wider environmental, social, economic and political systems (Klinke and Renn 2006, Briggs 2008). Systemic risks require more integrated and possibly precautionary approaches to risk governance (Renn and Graham 2005). One of the characteristics of systemic risk problems is that systemic risks are under a distributed responsibility: everyone is responsible for a part of the system but no one has the legitimacy to act on the entire system. (IRGC 2018); this is clearly the case for the regulation of mixtures across different silos.

Other characteristics of systemic risks are the inherent substantial uncertainties, complexity and ambiguity of the problems. “Complexity” should here be understood as the difficulty to identify and quantify causal relationships between a variety of potential hazards and the multitude of potential effects following exposure (Renn 2008). “Uncertainty” pertains to a situation where the type or nature of any adverse effects, or the likelihood of these effects, cannot be described precisely. “Ambiguity” refers to a situation where several legitimate and meaningful interpretations of accepted risk assessment results coexist. Subsequently, it is quite common to encounter ambiguity about normative values and ethical norms. Examples are questions about what specific societal problems in relation to human exposure to mixtures are selected for (further) scientific study; or the question whether the gathered weight of evidence warrants a certain degree of precautionary action; or which format and main message are selected for the communication of the ultimate study results (see also Elliot, 2017). Since answers to such questions are by nature value-laden, they inherently transcend scientific discourse. Therefore, such problems ask for a broader involvement of actors in the governance approach than (regulatory) experts alone as depicted in the figure below.

Figure 2: Risk escalator (Renn and Graham 2005)

The need for a broader dialogue and interaction between multiple parties on the governance of mixture health risks, from the perspective in figure 2, underscores the importance of the development of a joint vocabulary for the parties involved. So far, most of the dialogue on mixture risks has remained within the domain of regulators and experts. This would suffice for a ‘simple’ risk problem, but not for a systemic risk as mixtures. In anticipation of the outcomes of the various HJMP and other studies, a broad stakeholder dialogue on possible action perspectives and governance strategies toward mixtures is needed.

4.4 Views on governance of mixture risks

There are numerous examples of environmental health risk issues where experts disagree about whether apparent exposure levels can in fact adversely impact public health¹ or the environment. This is even more so when the discourse is widened to perspectives of stakeholders and particularly true for uncertain, complex and ambiguous risk problems such as mixtures. To our knowledge, an analysis of the argumentation on governance of mixtures has not taken place yet. Such an analysis does exist for the debates between endocrine disrupting substances (EDS) experts. This group of substances form a mixture in itself. Clahsen and colleagues have performed an argumentation analyses on two scientific publications on EDS (Lamb 2014, Bergman 2015) science using pragma-dialectical argumentation theory (PDAT) (Clahsen 2018). In their argumentation analysis, the structure of the argumentation in both publications was reconstructed, main standpoints and arguments were identified, underlying unexpressed premises were made explicit and major differences in starting points were uncovered. While a full discussion of this paper is beyond the scope of this report, several key elements emerged that are also pertinent to the (future) debate about mixture risk assessment and governance. The five main differences in

¹ individual health risk as in clinical or forensic toxicology are outside of the scope of this manuscript. Causal inference on individual risks is even more complicated and would involve addressing things like individual polymorphisms and the risks from relevant co-factors for the individual.

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starting points identified could be divided in 'interpretative ambiguity' about underlying scientific evidence and 'normative ambiguity' about differences in broader norms and values (as in the classification of (Renn 2008). Normative differences in starting points showed resemblance with the typologies of expert roles as outlined in literature in the fields of 'Science and Technology Studies', 'Science Policy Studies', 'Politics of expertise', 'Post-normal Science' and 'Risk Governance' (Spruijt, Knol et al. 2014, Spruijt 2016). Notably, resemblance with the (Weiss 2003) role typology of the 'environmental absolutist', typically being an advocate of relatively early precautionary action, versus the 'scientific absolutist, typically being an advocate of 'science-based regulation' (Clahsen 2018). While the interpretative ambiguity in principle can be solved by executing the adagio 'more research is needed', this does not apply to normative ambiguity. The settlement of normative ambiguity requires the inclusion of broader stakeholder groups.

The two opposing groups of authors can also be viewed from the perspective of Advocacy Coalition Framework (ACF) (Sabatier 1993), a theoretical lens to investigate complex public policy questions. According to the ACF, stakeholders form 'advocacy coalitions' when they have the same 'policy core beliefs'. These are beliefs about the practical implementation of fundamental 'deep core beliefs' (e.g. preferences for free-market mechanisms versus preferences for strong legislative power) into the policy question at hand, here 'exposure to mixtures of EU population'. Due to the complex, uncertain and ambiguous nature of many environmental health issues, multiple advocacy coalitions often exist that have competing 'policy core beliefs'. When a scientific debate appears to be polarized, such as the debate studied in the Clahsen et al. (2018) paper, these competing scientific interpretations of evidence then allow for the scientific substantiation of the policy preferences of competing advocacy coalitions.

To further examine such mechanisms at the science-policy interface from a theoretical perspective, Clahsen and colleagues have reviewed and combined the ACF with seven other frameworks to analyse and better understand environmental health risk controversies. Their original aim was to be able to analyse why different countries regulate environmental health risks differently (Clahsen 2018). A visualisation of the conceptual relationships amongst the different frameworks is given in the figure below:

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Interaction between coalitions through the exchange of argumentation

Fig. 12. An overarching framework that visualizes the various (conceptual) relationships between the eight conceptual frameworks. Abbreviations of the names of the frameworks, printed in [BOLD CAPITALS] and in between square brackets, are used to signal that an idea or concept of that respective framework has been used as a source of inspiration for that specific section of the overarching framework. List of the abbreviations used: [SARF], Social Amplification of Risk Framework; [ACF], Advocacy Coalition Framework; [ARERMP], Advisory Roles of Experts in Risk Management Processes; [RAP], Risk Assessment Paradigm; [CTR], Cultural Theory of Risk; [HMNC], Hofstede's Model of National Cultures.

The overarching framework proposes two levels of analysis. The upper level of analysis (upper part of above figure) mainly draws from the Social Amplification of Risk Framework of Kasperson et al. (Kasperson, Renn et al. 1988) and the ACF. In this level, we propose that, over time, a polemic develops between various advocacy coalitions. The advocacy coalition whose arguments (and framings contained therein) amplify most strongly in society will be expected to dictate the political course of action. The lower level of the framework (lower part of above figure) expands on the idea that an advocacy coalition's argumentative moves are performed in accordance with predetermined sets of beliefs. Notably, when an advocacy coalition provides argumentation to support their specific policy preference, argumentation referring to scientific knowledge and argumentation referring to normative policy positions can go hand in hand. Moreover, these two types of argumentation should be distinguished from one another, since they are informed by different types of issue-specific beliefs. Clahsen et al. (Clahsen 2018) consider that professional knowledge and beliefs are inspired by professional contexts, such as the scientific paradigm and underlying principles referred to by pertinent experts, or their professional affiliation. Personal knowledge and beliefs are inspired by personal contexts, such as social norms and community culture (cf. Cultural Theory of Risk; (Douglas 1983) and the characteristics of one national culture (cf. Hofstede's Model of National Culture; (Hofstede 1980). Both types of beliefs are considered to follow from fundamental beliefs. This hierarchal approach to specific and broad beliefs is inspired by the hierarchal system of policy beliefs as proposed by the ACF (Sabatier 1993). The grid-group typology (Douglas and Wildavsky, 1983) and myths of nature (Schwartz 1990) and typologies of expert roles (Weiss 2003, Pielke 2007) could be used to pinpoint specific types of fundamental beliefs.

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Applying these insights to the issue of information needs, we consider that the (often normative) information needs questions formulated in section 4.4 will be answered differently by experts that have different policy preferences (i.e. subscribe to different advocacy coalitions, conceptually speaking). In fact, such positions can already be observed where some argue that actions are needed now (Altenburger 2018), while others maintain that first legal mandates need to be adapted.

In the event that differences of opinion between experts could be identified, it may be worthwhile to verify whether these differences are entirely matters of interpretative ambiguity (i.e. fully focusses on argumentation referring to scientific knowledge), or whether normative ambiguity, through argumentation referring to normative positions, is at stake. The former could be adequately addressed within the scientific community, whereas the latter requires multi-stakeholder approaches. Examples of such approaches are participatory discourses (IRGC, 2005; Renn, 2008) or 'extended peer-community' approaches (see e.g.(Ravetz 1999)).

Accordingly, we argue that given the strong emphasis of HBM4EU on the science-policy interaction, the presentation of HBM4EU results should address, where possible, the nature of the uncertainties involved, discriminating between interpretative and normative sources of ambiguity. This will allow for recommendations about further research to reduce interpretative uncertainties ("..more research is needed..."), as well as recommendations for further multi-stakeholder dialogue to address normative ambiguity (".. further stakeholder dialogue is needed...").

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5 Toward operationalisation of mixture risk governance information

5.1 A selection of statements

To further the debate on the questions in section 4.2, given the complexities we expect in the discourse on mixture risk governance outlined in 4.4, more insight is needed in mixture expert roles, stakeholder views and expectations and support for different action perspectives from various parties. To this end, we assembled a set of statements and questions, many of which include normative considerations or judgements. A selection of statements is given in the annex. The statements are directly taken from, or are inspired by, the scientific literature on risk governance (in a broad sense) and current discourse on mixture risk assessment and management (Dake 1992, Douglas 1992, Weiss 2003, Weiss 2006, Pielke 2007, Spruijt, Knol et al. 2014, Altenburger 2018, Clahsen 2018, Clahsen 2018, Spruijt 2018). They relate to:

1. Considerations about roles and responsibilities for government, industry and the general public in taking action to reduce mixture health risks where appropriate
2. Considerations about the need to adapt current regulations or practices to include mixture risks
3. Considerations about the need to act now, based on current insights, within current regulations
4. Considerations about drivers for and proportionality of actions to reduce mixture health risks where appropriate
5. Views on expert roles with respect to need for actions

While there is a substantial and rapidly growing literature on mixture risk assessment, there is relatively little specific literature on views with respect to mixture risk management and governance. We therefore tested a selection of questions specifically targeted to mixtures. We first tested these internally and adapted accordingly. We then proceeded to test the questions on ten Dutch experts on food safety, consumer products, chemical safety and policy makers from ministries involved in health protection and environment. Further, we started interviewing international experts selected from the HJMPs; so far, five interviews were performed; more interviews are needed to enlarge the scope. To add further background to the delineation of the current discourse on risk assessment and management, selected statements and questions were also discussed at several meetings with experts and stakeholders, e.g. on a National Hub gathering. This was done on the basis of convenience and not in a systematic fashion.

The set of questions used in the latter group is presented in the table below. People were invited to participate through an e-mail request for a telephone interview. All answers and responses are treated confidentially, and cannot be attributed to specific individuals from specific organisations.

After introducing the topics, an open structured interview took place, allowing respondents to ask for clarification as well as allowing the interviewer to elaborate and ask follow up questions for clarification.

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Question 1	If we assume that avoiding exposure to mixtures is impossible in our modern society, which parties are responsible for reducing these exposures if the risks are considered too high? How would you describe this responsibility?
Question 2	<p>What role do scientists have in advising policy makers?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sticking to scientifically established facts and limiting interaction with policy makers (pure scientist) • Answering specific factual questions posed by policy makers (science arbiter) • Limiting options by promoting a specific policy that seems best (issue advocate) • Clarifying the various options available to policy makers (honest broker)
Question 3	Which criteria would you consider to be most important when determining what measures should be taken to reduce an established risk with regards to a mixture of chemicals? Could you make a top 3?
Question 4	The current legislation is based on the distinction between intentional, unintentional, and coincidental mixtures. Is this distinction useful in practise to reduce the risk of mixtures?
Question 5	What are the most important obstacles for different Directorates – DGs (silos) to work together to regulate the risks of mixtures?
Question 6	To what extent would you take a subjective feeling of safety amongst the population into account if it contradicts scientifically established facts, while making a policy plan?

5.2 The results from the interviews

We approached a convenience sample of experts representing domains of 'Ministry of Health', 'Ministry of Environment', or similar EC DG's and research institutes and agencies dealing with risk assessment of chemicals from environment and food sectors. In the initial contacts with potential interviewees, we stressed that all information and opinions provided would be treated as strictly confidential, without reference to the individual or his/her affiliation. Thus, respondents were able to provide personal opinions, without the need to express the 'official institute's' position (in discussions in the Horizon2020 Mixture project Cooperation meetings, some individuals noted that they found it difficult to deviate from the official position of their employer).

Respondents were first recruited from the Netherlands and subsequently from contacts from the Horizon2020 Mixture project Cooperation. Unfortunately, the respondents from latter group turned to be difficult to recruit for telephone interviews; possibly because opinions were already expressed at joint meetings and/or because some of the projects were in their final reporting period and struggling with deadlines. As a result, we interviewed 15 respondents, nine from the Netherlands and six from other EU countries.

The following table shows the main standpoints that arose from the responses to the six questions that were posed in the interviews. The consulted number of experts and policy makers was approximately the same (50/50). The answers have been shortened to increase clarity by providing an overview of the most important statements. That way it is easier to find the similarities and differences in opinions with regards to the questions asked.

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Question 1: If we assume that avoiding exposure to mixtures is impossible in our modern society, which parties are responsible for reducing these exposures if the risks are considered too high? How would you describe this responsibility?

R1 (NL)	<p>The industry has the main responsibility for guaranteeing the safety of mixtures</p> <p>The government should make a legislation that requires transparency</p> <p>Relevant institutions like food safety agencies and the like should keep an eye out and remain alert</p> <p>Citizens have the responsibility towards society to live a healthy life as far as they have a choice</p>
R2 (NL)	<p>The industry is responsible for the chemicals they produce</p> <p>In the case multiple parties are responsible for a mixture, it is up to policy makers to regulate the exposure</p> <p>NGO's should help decrease exposure to mixtures</p> <p>Citizens should decrease their own exposure to mixtures</p>
R3 (NL)	<p>All parties are equally responsible</p> <p>The industry is responsible for the safety of the chemicals they produce</p> <p>The government is responsible for the admission of these chemicals</p> <p>Citizens should avoid (voluntary) exposure</p>
R4 (NL)	<p>The government holds the primary responsibility. They should implement rules for the industry and ensure compliance.</p>
R5 (NL)	<p>In practise, the only trustworthy party to reduce exposure to mixtures is the government. Citizens do not have sufficient knowledge and the industry has other motives.</p>
R6 (NL)	<p>The industry holds the primary responsibility</p> <p>The government and businesses can make sure the rules are abided</p> <p>Citizens can reduce voluntary exposure</p>
R7 (NL)	<p>The industry and the government have the main responsibility</p> <p>The government should set the rules that should be abided by the industry</p> <p>Scientists and NGOs have a secondary responsibility</p> <p>Citizens are not responsible, as they do not have the right tools</p>
R8 (NL)	<p>The industry is responsible for their own chemicals</p> <p>The government should set the rules and make sure they are abided by the industry</p> <p>Citizens are not responsible, unless they are fully informed and exposure is not the result of neglect of higher institutions</p>
R9 (NL)	<p>All parties have a responsibility</p> <p>The industry should ensure their chemicals are safe</p>

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	<p>The government should check whether their (industries') research and data is honest and conduct research themselves</p> <p>Consumer organisations can put pressure on the industry</p> <p>NGOs can make a noise when there is a possible threat to public health</p> <p>Citizens should put pressure on the industry and be willing to pay more for safety</p>
R10 (EU)	<p>All parties are responsible</p> <p>The industry should ensure they produce safe products</p> <p>The government and scientists should do research on exposure</p> <p>Consumer organisations should keep an eye out for loop holes in the law</p> <p>Citizens can make a difference if they have enough health literacy</p>
R11 (EU)	<p>All parties are responsible</p> <p>Citizens are responsible for voluntary exposure</p> <p>The government should characterise the risk, inform the population and regulate the exposure</p> <p>The industry should do their own research and make sure the risks are clear, but socioeconomics should be taken into account (the benefits should outweigh the costs)</p> <p>Consumer organisations and NGO's should remain objective and true to science, and not spread "nonsense"</p>
R12 (EU)	<p>Policy makers/risk managers (increase exposure safety margin)</p> <p>Industry (use other methodology that tests the whole mixture, use least hazardous compounds, provide information throughout the chain, use interdisciplinary approach)</p> <p>Businesses (place higher standards when buying products – focus on sustainability across the life cycle)</p> <p>Citizens should not be expected to know about and avoid exposure to mixtures</p>
R13 (EU)	<p>The industry should reduce unintentional emissions, find safe alternatives (also without external pressure), be more proactive, and reduce toxicity to a minimum</p> <p>The government should come up with effective legislation</p> <p>NGOs should put pressure on the industry and inform citizens about current exposure</p> <p>Citizens should reduce any exposure to mixtures if they can</p>
R14 (EU)	<p>It depends on the type of mixture. In the case of intentional mixtures every party plays a role to ensure a safe product. Levels of safety should be guaranteed, therefore citizens have no responsibility – unless they are informed about risks of unintentional mixtures.</p>
R15 (EU)	<p>There is a shared responsibility.</p>

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	<p>Primary: the producers. Business should take more measures in reducing the exposure to mixtures.</p> <p>Second: the government. They should regulate the exposure to mixtures and react to current risks.</p> <p>To a lesser extent: consumers. They could develop habits to adapt to the exposure.</p> <p>Consumer organisations and NGOs should provide information, communicate the concern of the population to the authorities, identify and highlight certain issues, ensure the advice is followed</p>
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Question 2: What role do scientists have in advising policy makers?

- Sticking to scientifically established facts and limiting interaction with policy makers (pure scientist)
- Answering specific factual questions posed by policy makers (science arbiter)
- Limiting options by promoting a specific policy that seems best (issue advocate)
- Clarifying the various options available to policy makers (honest broker)

R1 (NL)	Pure scientist and science arbiter. Scientists deliver the information, the policy maker decides. Ideally a shift would happen that allowed more social/political involvement, but scientists don't have that knowledge yet.
R2 (NL)	Honest broker. It does not stop with risk assessment. They should sketch the consequences of certain decisions.
R3 (NL)	Pure scientist. The scientist should deliver the information, clarify the methodology and provide information on epidemiology. They should not be involved in making a policy plan.
R4 (NL)	Pure scientist and honest broker. Scientists should ensure that policy makers share the same knowledge on methodologies and data. Transparency is important. They should think about consequences of various options without making the actual decision.
R5 (NL)	Honest broker. Pure scientist does not exist. They can advise, but not promote or make the policy plan, as they do not have sufficient knowledge on politics and social consequences of decisions.
R6 (NL)	Pure scientist, science arbiter and honest broker. They should provide information on the methodology and consequences, but not make the final decision.
R7 (NL)	All four. Scientists should explain the methodology, share insights and suggest certain policies.
R8 (NL)	A mix of all four. Scientist should share insight, clarify methodologies, sketch consequences of a decision, and make suggestions. They should not take the lead however.
R9 (NL)	Honest broker. Providing insight into the possibilities and consequences, while remaining as objective as possible.

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R10 (EU)	It depends on the topic and the level of knowledge of the scientist. Political issues are too complex, so issue advocate is the least ideal. The roles should be strictly defined per situation.
R11 (EU)	All four, dependending on the situation and the type of scientist. Scientists should also be concerned about the consequences in society, and policy makers should also take science into account.
R12 (EU)	Science arbiter and honest broker. Pure scientist does not exist. Issue advocate only when nobody else is doing it. In addition: scientists should translate scientific knowledge to ordinary people.
R13 (EU)	All of them. Issue advocate the least as it is not good to be blind to other options.
R14 (EU)	It depends on the type of scientist. Scientists from academic institutions should clarify the methodology, be alert, and inform policy makers. Regulatory scientists should assess the evidence of the data, produce recommendations and be proactive.
R15 (EU)	Honest knowledge broker. On the condition that it is based on technical scientific facts: main contributions, sources of exposure, clear view of the impact certain measures may have. The choices are up to the policy makers.

Question 3: Which criteria would you consider to be most important when determining what measures should be taken to reduce an established risk with regards to a mixture of chemicals? Could you make a top 3?

R1 (NL)	1 Nature of the effect 2 Nature of the exposure 3 The scope of the effect
R2 (NL)	1 Economic considerations 2 Nature of the exposure 3 The scope of the effect
R3 (NL)	1 Nature of the exposure 2 Nature of the effect 3 Economic considerations
R4 (NL)	1 Nature of the effect 2 Nature of the exposure 3 Economic considerations
R5 (NL)	Question unclear
R6 (NL)	1 Nature of the effect 2 Scope of the effect 3 Economic considerations
R7 (NL)	1 Scope of the effect

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 Nature of the effect 3 Economic considerations
R8 (NL)	Impossible to generalise, as it depends on which criteria have the highest score per case
R9 (NL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Nature of the effect 2 Scope of the effect 3 Nature of the exposure
R10 (EU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Scope of the effect 2 Nature of the effect 3 Other: concern amongst the population
R11 (EU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1: Nature of the effect (seriousness) 2: Scope of the effect (number of children) 3: Nature of the exposure (involuntary)
R12 (EU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Nature of the effect 2 Other: feasibility 3 Nature of the exposure <p>In addition: social/environmental justice should also be on the agenda</p>
R13 (EU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Nature of the exposure 2 Nature of the effect 3 Scope of the effect
R14 (EU)	<p>It depends on the kind of risk and the level of the risk.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Other (look for alternatives or ways to mitigate) 2 Other (oversee the consequences of the alternatives) 3 Other (depends on how much we are willing to pay for safety)
R15 (EU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The nature of the effect 2. The scope of the effect 3. The nature of the exposure
Question 4: The current legislation is based on the distinction between intentional, unintentional, and coincidental mixtures. Is this distinction useful in practise to reduce the risk of mixtures?	
R1 (NL)	Only in the sense that great disasters hardly ever occur anymore. There is not enough knowledge about actual exposure to have an effective legislation.

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R2 (NL)	Yes, it is effective for intentional mixtures. Especially in the case of unintentional mixtures, legislation is not effective enough to avoid risks.
R3 (NL)	Risk assessment and methodologies are not sufficiently developed to be able to come up with an effective legislation for the different types of mixtures.
R4 (NL)	The point is not whether it is an intentional or unintentional mixture, but the fact that we are exposed to a combination of these types. The current legislation does not take this into account.
R5 (NL)	As far as I know there is no legislation on mixtures. This is mainly because we lack information and data on exposure.
R6 (NL)	At first glance, the legislation for intentional mixture seems effective, but it does not take into account that we are exposed to different types of mixtures from several sources every day.
R7 (NL)	No idea. There is not enough knowledge, not even for intentional mixtures.
R8 (NL)	I don't have enough knowledge on legislation. Coincidental mixtures are impossible to test.
R9 (NL)	I do not have enough knowledge on legislation.
R10 (EU)	Unclear. There is not enough knowledge to have an adequate legislation. If the knowledge becomes available, adequate legislation will surely follow.
R11 (EU)	Yes, because different companies make their own product. It is impossible to demand from all of these companies to stop making the product, unless it is an intentional mixture, of which the effect is proven.
R12 (EU)	No. The legislation should be more similar to pharmaceuticals: upstream design with the final product in mind, to avoid being unaware of by-products.
R13 (EU)	The distinction is only useful for intentional mixtures, as it is assessed before it arrives on the market. Legislation for unintentional and coincidental mixtures is too fragmented.
R14 (EU)	Only intentional mixtures can be regulated – the rest is impossible to regulate as each person is exposed to different mixtures every day.
R15 (EU)	Yes, it is useful. With intentional mixtures it is clearer to know who to target in taking measures, what the cause and effect is, what the alternatives could be. In the case of coincidental mixtures this is all unclear, the sources, how it can be avoided. In the case of unintentional mixtures, it might be easier if the cause is clear. You know how to address it when the byproduct of the life cycle is unacceptable.

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Question 5: What are the most important obstacles for different Directorates – DGs (silos) to work together to regulate the risks of mixtures?

R1 (NL)	There is not enough collaboration, but we need different fields to work together (for instance, we need psychologists and sociologists to help increase trust in the population).
R2 (NL)	They need to operate from one vision; the perspectives of different DGs may conflict, as a decision that benefits public health may harm the environment and vice versa.
R3 (NL)	Different DGs have different interests that may clash. Citizens hold the key to solving this political problem, as public health is as much their concern as it is for the government and health institutes.
R4 (NL)	There should be more collaboration and more shared knowledge on different fields, so that we can solve the puzzle together.
R5 (NL)	No comment
R6 (NL)	No obstacles
R7 (NL)	There is not enough collaboration between DGs. This has to do with the fact that several laws and rules are not connected.
R8 (NL)	I don't know. It hardly occurred. Sometimes it is noticeable that different interests play a role.
R9 (NL)	Because of the structure in hierarchical organisations, it is hard for good ideas to be communicated upstream. The budget is also too tight, and the responsibilities too strictly defined.
R10 (EU)	Different interests can lead to possible conflicts, but this is merely a fact and not an obstacle.
R11 (EU)	Departments have close contact with the 'Public Centre for Social Welfare' so as to bridge silos. Bringing DGs together should be organised, based on weighing the pros and cons of scientific questions on what has priority, is attainable and proven. Translating this into mixtures is difficult, but important.
R12 (EU)	We need a policy across the legislative silos to provide an incentive across the silos. We should create something new, instead of wanting to change the status quo. Changing leads to low priority and resistance.
R13 (EU)	Sectorial regulation is the problem, not the DGs themselves. Different areas have different DGs that are bound by requirements, which make the connection difficult. Common concerns, for instance about EDS, can be addressed in a horizontal exchange, by referring to the precautionary principle.

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R14 (EU)	I don't see any obstacles. What is needed is more scientific knowledge on key combinations and food consumption.
R15 (EU)	What we need is undisputed scientific evidence – then all the other obstacles will disappear. Other obstacles may be different angles, benefits, and effects on several health domains.
Question 6: To what extent would you take a subjective feeling of safety amongst the population into account if it contradicts scientifically established facts, while making a policy plan?	
R1 (NL)	It is important to try and console the population, without losing a grip on reality. In some cases, if there is a lot of distrust it might be good to remove the chemicals from the market.
R2 (NL)	It is necessary to stay true to the facts, but provide information and be aware of the perception of the risk to anticipate the responses.
R3 (NL)	There should be a response to concerns of the population. Even if a risk is small, if the population does not wish to be exposed it would be fair to remove the mixture from the market.
R4 (NL)	Scientists should remain objective and inform citizens. They should not be affected by emotions of the population, as this could lead from bad to worse.
R5 (NL)	If science proves it is not unsafe, I would not remove it from the market. There should be openness about possible risks, as often we do not know whether it is safe or unsafe because of a lack of research. It is important to think about how to explain this to the population.
R6 (NL)	Chemicals should not be banned because of public concern, as this can lead to random decisions and not necessarily to an improvement of public health. Providing information is important.
R7 (NL)	Risk communication is equally important to the actual risk, apart from the fact that it sometimes appears there was a risk after all.
R8 (NL)	If there is no actual threat, it is best to only provide information and start a dialogue with the person or organisation that created this concern.
R9 (NL)	Public perception always affects policy, it determines the plan. How this happens is different case by case.
R10 (EU)	If there is concern that is a type of adverse health effect, so it is important to educate and console people to increase trust.
R11 (EU)	Don't get involved in chemophobia. Voluntary exposure is more harmful than involuntary exposure, but the emotional response to the latter is more extreme, because of the uncertainty. Awareness is important. The social costs. We should communicate carefully and from a place of honesty and knowledge.

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R12 (EU)	It is better to be safe than sorry; we are over relying on a limited set of data. If there is no data it should not be on the market. It should be transparent. Undermining trust is bad.
R13 (EU)	Science should be translated to easy to understand language. Don't remove safe chemicals from the market, but improve health literacy. Avoid confusion by being honest, also about uncertainties.
R14 (EU)	Increase health literacy, including informing citizens about the fact that there is always a level of risk. Describe the possible consequences of mixtures that are currently in the media.
R15 (EU)	If there is concern, but the scientific facts are clear, then it is our task to put the fact rights in lay language. If it is unclear and the nature of the effect may be severe, then precautionary measures should be taken. As an authority you should always be honest about uncertainties, because NGOs will exploit them anyway. Honesty will increase trust.

5.3 Summary

A recurrent theme in the question on roles and responsibilities with regards to the reduction of exposure to mixtures is the question whether the industry holds the main responsibility or the government. Many respondents argued that all parties were considered to be equally responsible for different tasks. When one party had priority, most of the time the industry was seen as the most responsible party, as they are the ones producing the chemicals and indirectly creating the mixture. However, as one industry can be responsible for merely part of a mixture, who is responsible for the whole mixture? Because of this issue, and also because the industry might not be objective, the government is sometimes seen as the party responsible for making sure the research on mixtures is sound and the industry abides the rules set out for them. NGOs and consumer organisations are consistently seen as the ones putting pressure on the industry/government and making a sound when safety is not guaranteed. There was a difference of opinion concerning the question whether citizens had any responsibility at all; whether they were responsible for avoiding voluntary exposure or should be able to trust they are not put at risk.

The current legislation was consistently perceived as insufficient or inadequate, not necessarily because of the legislation itself, but the lack of information and data on mixtures. Some respondents held the opinion that intentional mixtures were well covered by the legislation, but this would not be the case for the other types. A commonly heard criticism on the legislation was that it was too fragmented and did not take into account exposure to a combination of mixtures from several sources. This would mean that legislation is hypothetically possible for intentional mixtures, but this would not cover actual exposure as it is always a combination in reality.

Although occasionally the collaboration between DGs was seen as unproblematic, many times it has been mentioned that a conflict of interests is the main obstacle to solving the problem together. Also scientific uncertainty has been suggested as the cause. Once it had been mentioned that the hierarchy in certain organisations may obstruct good ideas, and once that an obstacle would be that changing the status quo is not encouraged. In addition, it appears that a significant number of

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the respondents feel there is not enough collaboration in the first place, and one suggested that collaboration between DGs should be organised.

The question about expert roles seemed to get relatively consistent responses. In some cases, a mix of all four was preferred depending on the situation and the knowledge of that particular scientist. The scientist was generally expected to provide insight, explain methodologies, and give an overview of options and possible consequences. Honest broker was mentioned most frequently, and issue advocate the least. Generally, it was not considered ideal for a scientist to suggest a certain policy as the knowledge on social and economic consequences would be limited.

The question about risk communication evoked many responses. Trust is seen as an important factor, but the way trust is earned is perceived differently. On the one hand banning chemicals from the market to increase trust was mentioned, but also the opposite – that this would lead to more questions. The idea of removing chemicals from the market and abide the wishes of the population stood in contrast with the idea that banning would lead to arbitrary decisions, possibly from bad to worse and would not necessarily benefit public health. Increasing health literacy was consistently mentioned as an important factor in risk communication, as well as being honest about scientific uncertainties.

5.4 Do the questions differentiate between different viewpoints?

Most questions seem to be able to differentiate between different viewpoints held by the consulted experts regarding to the reduction of exposure to mixtures in our modern society. However, as some questions were either unclear or the topic too nuanced for a black and white answer, not all questions may be suitable for a web-based survey.

Question 1 evoked ideas about different types of responsibilities and showed that different opinions exist concerning who holds the primary responsibility and who should not have any responsibility at all. Ideas held by the respondents about the responsibility of citizens and the industry was ambiguous. Therefore, this question differentiates between several viewpoints and can evoke responses that show where the disagreement exists.

Question 2 was sufficiently clear in spite of possible unfamiliarity with Pielke and Weiss' typology. The answers indicate that experts do not share the same preference when it comes to roles adopted by scientists in relation to policy makers, although the role of issue advocate was the least preferred. It appears that not all experts believe in the role of an 'objective' scientist and that the ideal role may differ depending on the expertise of that particular scientist and the organisation he or she is working for. The responses to this question cover the main ideas about the roles scientists should adopt while interacting with policy makers. As the ideal roles may be dependent on the situation, in a web-based survey it should be taken into account that the single statement that should be scored must specify this.

Question 3 needed a lot of further explanation and clarification; it cannot be used in a web-based survey approach. It should be removed from the list and not be used as a basis for a list of relevant statements. After initial reformulation of the question and the categories, the clarity had somewhat improved, but responses consistently show that it is difficult to make a hierarchy as the importance of the criteria can only be seen in relation to other criteria and not separately. Also, the most important criteria would be case dependent, and it is therefore too simplistic to draw a simple hierarchy that can be applied in every case.

Question 4 is probably more suitable for an interview than an online survey, as it did lead to interesting statements, but they sometimes deviated from the question. When the respondents stayed true to the question, it often appeared that either the respondent did not have sufficient

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knowledge on current legislation, or he or she had a lot of knowledge, and was specifically asking what part of the legislation was referred to, as no black and white answer could be provided about a legislation that is so complex. The distinction between unintentional and coincidental mixtures was unclear to some policy makers. It may help to provide clear definitions of these.

The responses to question 5 were diverse. Some respondents named common obstacles with regards to the collaboration between different DGs, while others found no obstacles at all, or had not experienced any collaboration. If extended to other countries and the EU (which still needs to be corroborated), this question potentially shows the contrasting ideas held about the quality of collaboration between different DGs.

Question 6 brought about many ideas about improving trust amongst citizens. It showed where the most important obstacles are and evoked different opinions about how far policies should go in improving trust amongst citizens. Therefore, this question is helpful in starting a discussion that could lead to fruitful ideas about the roles of citizens, government, health institutions and the media in improving the relationship between the government and citizens and providing realistic information about the possible dangers of mixtures in modern society.

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6 Discussion

Information needs on mixtures was operationalised as “How can we effectively and efficiently manage the health risks associated with chemical mixtures in the European population in such a way that residual mixture risks are considered acceptable from a public health and personal health point of view, while maintaining to the degree possible the societal and personal benefits of the products that lead to the mixture exposures”. There currently is little direct literature to address this information need. In the absence of much pertinent literature, we took the concept of ‘information need’ from Taylor as starting point, translated this to the issues of mixture risk assessment and management and combined this with concepts from different domains, notably from, risk governance and argumentation theory, building on the integrative framework developed by Clahsen and colleagues, and on earlier discussion with representatives of the Horizon2020 Mixture project cooperation of HBM4EU with EDC-MixRisk, EuroMix, EU-ToxRisk, SOLUTIONS.

From the context of the Science-Policy interface in HBM4EU, we first set out to interview experts and policy makers, using a set of structured interview questions, so as to collect first insights into the current thinking and argumentation by these professionals. We see this as essential first elements to identify wider information needs. Unfortunately, the interviewed experts were biased toward one country (NL) with nine respondents from NL and six from other EU MS. Repeated efforts to engage more experts and policy makers from other countries did not sufficiently expand the scope of interviewees. Nonetheless, the variety of opinions witnessed in the discussions at meetings of the Horizon2020 Mixture project cooperation were also well reflected in the responses from the interviews. Overall, this effort needs further expansion to stakeholder groups from other countries and international institutions to reflect a broader scope of opinions held by experts and policy makers. Approaches such as earlier proposed in an Internal Call proposal for a Pan European Risk Perception survey could be taken as a starting point to initiate such an activity. The IC proposed a set of potential approaches, such as (a combination of) focus group consultation, (web-based) Delphi study, and/or web-based questionnaire survey or Q-method survey. Obviously, the content focus would need to be redirected to mixtures.

Given the laborious process of recruitment of respondents, and the execution, analysis and reporting of the interviews, alternative approaches such as a web-based survey or Q-methodology approaches should be considered, to allow a more quantitative assessment. While there currently are various approaches to describe risks of mixtures, such as the Hazard Index, the Point of Departure Index and the Cumulative Assessment Group approach (see AD15.1), these are still rather in their infancy and guidance or benchmarks for acceptable risks levels are as yet not broadly established, nor are they fully embedded in most current regulations on chemicals.

There is a variety of opinions about the criteria to determine which measures to take to reduce mixture health risks when considered unacceptable. Nature and scope of the health effect were commonly mentioned. Some consider the nature of the exposure and feasibility to reduce exposures. Others consider economic considerations, concern in the population and social justice aspects. Most prefer to take the particular context into consideration, above defining ‘general principles’. This would be in line with the risk governance approach for uncertain, complex and ambiguous risk problems and with the ‘systemic risk’ nature of mixtures.

These observations have important implications for the information needs, and therefore for the type of information to be provided by the experts to the policy makers. The manifestation of mixture risks should be described in nature, scope and magnitude, since this is a commonly mentioned criterion as a response to question 3 (Which criteria would you consider to be most important when determining what measures should be taken to reduce an established risk with regards to a

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mixture of chemicals? Could you make a top 3?). As it appeared to be the case that generalisations and making a hierarchy was often perceived as impossible without a specific context, drivers of the mixture risks as well as the societal benefits of such drivers would need to be clarified to allow socio-economic cost-benefit considerations. In addition, to allow social justice considerations, specific risk groups should be identified; inclusion of public concern in strategies to deal with mixture risks, commensurate with governance of systemic risks, would necessitate further 'concern assessment', e.g. through stakeholder dialogue and focus group discussions.

Opinions also vary about responsibilities of different parties in reducing mixture health risks. Clearly, governments and industry have responsibilities here. Some also see a role for the public, to reduce exposure to mixtures through lifestyle choices. The latter has consequences for the information provision to the general public.

Potential problems in cooperation between silo's from different policy domains (like DG's) are seen as mainly stemming from differences in regulations and the absence of a common regulatory framework; there is a call to provide such a common framework.

The distinction of mixtures into intentional and others is sometimes seen as useful; a 'whole mixture approach' can in principle be taken for intentional mixtures, although that still does not include possible interaction of the intentional mixture with other mixture exposures. An overarching legislation that takes combinations of mixture effects into account is needed, as it represents a more realistic picture of actual daily exposure.

Overall, the opinions on information needs to serve the development of risk governance policies for mixture risks are still rather vague and not yet clearly outlined. This limits our ability to translate the consequences for HBM mixture information functionality.

After the first delineation of the variety of views and resulting diversity in information needs, a wider dialogue needs to be established. Firstly, to broaden the scope and views of interviewees to include members of the general public, NGO's and industry. Secondly, to inform further requirements for future risk governance approaches toward management of mixture health risks, which in essence is a uncertain, complex and ambiguous risk problem, or in governance terms a 'wicked problem'.

We also want to point out here, that the set of questions and statements in current form has not yet been tested in a wider audience, e.g. in a pilot study. In the international context of HBM4EU, statements and questions would need to be translated and back-translated into local languages before application.

The proposed broader development of the dialogue is as yet unplanned in HBM4EU, but could potentially be established through cooperation with WP's from Pillar 1 and/or through the Internal Call mechanism.

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7 Conclusions

- Mixtures can be viewed as ‘systemic risks’ given the properties of uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity and the general ‘embeddedness’ of chemicals in daily life; risk governance approaches should be targeted as such and the contextual aspects may require tailored approaches instead of generic regulation.
- The information needs from policy makers and experts are still rather diffuse and unarticulated, in line with the ‘systemic risk’ nature of mixtures.
- Since the information needs are not sufficiently articulated, consequences for functionality of HBM mixture data cannot directly be derived as yet.
- As can be expected from the literature on systemic risks, views on responsibilities and criteria to guide risk reduction strategies vary considerably; this warrant further exploration of views and mental models held by the stakeholders involved.
- A broader dialogue on information needs for mixture risk governance with stakeholders is needed, but as yet not planned. Any such exercise, within HBM4EU, should be done in conjunction with Pillar 1.

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8 Recommendations

It is recommended to initiate discussions in the Management Board on the need and merit of a broader dialogue on information needs for mixture risk governance in HBM4EU. Such a dialogue would have a Pan European nature, involve experts, policymakers and stakeholder/interest groups.

The earlier Internal Call proposal (August 2018) on a Pan European Risk Perception Survey, could be revisited as a starting point to initiate such dialogue, although the focus would need to be redirected toward mixtures per se. This might entail (a combination of) focus group consultation, (web-based) Delphi study, and/or web-based questionnaire survey or Q-method survey. Such an activity must build on earlier HBM4EU work in WP4 (the organization of a citizen survey & focus group).

Since the IC procedure is time consuming, a more direct approach by the MB to initiate further work could be considered, e.g. invite WP4 to develop approaches, potentially in liaison with WP5, WP7 and WP15.

HBM4EU

science and policy
for a healthy future

HORIZON2020 Programme
Contract No. 733032 HBM4EU

9 Annex 1- Policy brief for the mixtures group of HMB4EU priority substances

Policy brief for the mixtures group of HMB4EU priority substances

Negotiated procedure No EEA/IEA/17/001

For EEA

5 July 2017

RPA
Risk & Policy Analysts

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Policy brief for the mixtures group of HMB4EU priority substances

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9.1 Identification and classification

Overview: Identity and classification

Where the other groups of substances being investigated in the HBM4EU project are comprised of individual named substances (with the possible exception of emerging substances), the chemical mixtures group represents a much broader field of investigation focussing on the combined effects of two or more substances. In principle, a mixture is any combination of chemical substances or their metabolites whether developed intentionally (for example, as a product) or occurring unintentionally in the environment or within organisms such as humans (which are the focus for HBM).

As a mixture can be any combination of substances, the number of possible combinations as chemical mixtures is, in principle, approaching the infinite.

Work on the chemical mixtures HBM4EU group aims to improve the ability of HBM to inform science, policy and regulatory actions with respect to identifying mixtures with the potential to

Identity and links to information

From an HBM perspective, a mixture is any combination of substances circulating simultaneously in the body originating from:

- simultaneous exposure to two or more substances from a single common source across single exposure routes;
- simultaneous exposure to two or more substances from multiple sources, exposure routes and pathways;
- repeated or chronic exposure to substances from multiple sources across multiple pathways; or
- any combination of the above.

Given the large number of substances to which individuals may be exposed, the range of exposure routes, pathways and timescales as well as modes of action, identifying which combinations and sources represent a risk is a significant challenge to both experimental and observational science and to regulators seeking scientific assessment of risks for the regulation of substances and chemical risk management regulation.

Work on the chemical mixtures HBM4EU group aims to improve the ability of HBM to inform science, policy and regulatory actions with respect to identifying mixtures with the potential to cause adverse effects and dealing with them. There is, at present, no definitive list of priority mixtures that can be reported on within this profile. For the purposes of setting out current legislative arrangements regarding mixtures it is useful to distinguish between different types of mixtures using the categories set out in ongoing European Commission work.

The European Commission communication on “*The combination effects of chemicals – Chemical mixtures*”² was published in response to a request from the European Parliament for the Commission to consider the extent to which the existing legislation “*adequately addresses risks*

² European Commission (2012): Communication from the Commission to the Council: The combination effects of chemicals – Chemical mixtures, COM(2012) 252 final, Brussels, 31.5.2012. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52012DC0252>

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from exposure to multiple chemicals from different sources and pathways, and on this basis to consider appropriate modifications, guidelines and assessment methods". In the communication mixtures are differentiated as follows:

- **Intentional mixtures:** these are manufactured formulated products that are marketed as such. The composition of such mixtures and the hazardous properties and classification of the constituents is known;
- **Mixtures originating from a single source:** also known as 'unintentional mixtures'³ these are the result of discharges to the environment during the production, transport, use or disposal of goods, often contain a mixture of chemical substances. The composition can either be known (for example an effluent) or it can be unknown; and
- **Mixtures of chemicals originating from multiple sources and through multiple pathways:** also known as "coincidental mixtures"^{Fehler! Textmarke nicht definiert.} these relate to multiple substances from multiple and varying sources. Their composition is unknown and can vary in both space and time.

³ See Kienzler, A., Bopp, S., van der Linden, S., Berggren, E., Worth, A., (2016), Regulatory assessment of chemical mixtures: Requirements, current approaches and future perspectives. Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology. <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0273230016301337#>

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9.2 Lifecycle uses and exposure

Overview: Identity and classification

As a mixture can be any combination of substances, the number of possible combinations as chemical mixtures is, in principle, approaching the infinite.

With the possible exception of the intentional (manufactured) mixtures, the uses, lifecycles and, ultimately, sources of potential human exposure to unintentional and coincidental mixtures are numerous and largely unknown/unquantified.

The figure below serves to illustrate the many pathways through which humans may be exposed to different chemicals and different combinations of chemicals over time. Whilst it is likely that far from all of the exposures combined may pose a risk, with the exception of manufactured intentional mixtures, as was concluded in the Commission Communication² “*within the framework of EU legislation there is [as yet] no mechanism for a systematic, comprehensive and integrated assessment of mixture effects taking into account different routes of exposure and different product types*”.

Human exposure to chemicals throughout their life-cycle

After: Prüss-Ustün et al (2011): Knowns and unknowns on burden of disease due to chemicals: a systematic review, *Environmental Health* 2011, 10:9
<http://www.ehjournal.net/content/10/1/9>

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9.3 Legislative status

Overview: Legislative status

The legislative status of mixtures varies depending on the type of mixture:

- **Intentional mixtures:** these are formulated products that marketed as such and so are covered by requirements under CLP, the authorisation of plant protection products as well as rules governing the composition of cosmetics and approval of medicinal products. For intentional mixtures, the composition is well known and the assessments are made based on the properties of the constituents supplemented, where appropriate (but often in exceptional circumstances), by tests carried out on the entire product;
- **Mixtures originating from a single source:** also known as 'unintentional mixtures'¹ these are the result of discharges to the environment during the production, transport, use or disposal of goods, often contain a mixture of chemical substances. The composition can either be known (for example an effluent) or it can be unknown. Where composition is known (or can be identified) assessments can be made based on knowledge of the constituents and where the composition is unknown an assessment can in principle be based on tests carried out on the whole mixture but, in practice, there are very few examples of EU legislation specifically requiring the assessment or testing of whole mixtures. The Water Framework Directive and also waste legislation have elements that require consideration of effects in combination; and
- **Mixtures of chemicals originating from multiple sources and through multiple pathways:** also known as "coincidental mixtures"² (Fehler! Textmarke nicht definiert.) these relate to multiple substances from multiple and varying sources. Their composition is unknown and can vary in both space and time and so, clearly, their identification is difficult. There is only a limited coverage of issues in EU legislation and these are

9.3.1 Intentional mixtures

Being formulated products, the chemical composition of intentional mixtures is well known. Further, owing to legislation that applies to individual chemicals, the physicochemical, toxicological and ecotoxicological properties of the substances making up a mixture are also known. Here, the first level of regulation is via the REACH Regulation (No 1907/2006) and the classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures regulation (CLP Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008).

9.3.1.1 Intentional mixtures under REACH

All chemical substances manufactured or imported in quantities of >1t per year per manufacturer/importer (MI) must be registered under REACH. In the process the REACH registration dossier must:

- provide the complete set of physico-chemical, toxicological and ecotoxicological information required under the regulation;
- make the appropriate classifications for and hazardous properties under CLP (Regulation EC 1272/2008);
- where hazardous properties are identified, communicate this to downstream users by means of Safety data Sheets (SDS);

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- for substances produced in quantities greater than 10t per year per MI carry out a chemical safety assessment (CSA) on all identified uses where this must demonstrate adequate control of any identified risks. The CSA comprises:
 - environmental and human health exposure assessment and PBT/vPvB screening and assessment (in the event of a positive result in screening);
 - where a substance meets one or more hazardous classifications under CLP or is identified as PBT/vPvB, risk characterisation and identification of risk control measures for identified uses;
 - communication of resulting information to downstream users via an extended Safety Data Sheet (eSDS) including the emissions scenarios for the identified uses and information on operating conditions (OC) and risk management measures (RMM).

Regarding the treatment of mixtures under REACH, the full set of requirements is complex but can be summarised as follows. The CSAs for substances must cover all identified uses during the substance's life. Where the substance is present in mixtures at levels above the cut-off values set out in CLP⁴ then uses in these mixtures must also be included in the CSA for the substance and information communicated to downstream users via the eSDS.

Under REACH, downstream users (including formulators) using the substance in mixtures above the cut-off values identified above must assess whether their uses are covered by the exposure scenarios provided in the eSDS supplied to them and whether the conditions of their own uses of the substance are consistent with those in the eSDS. If they are not action is required to have the use covered by CSA, implement conditions of use described in the emissions scenario or find a substitute. Again, information in the form of SDS must be passed further down the supply chain.

Under REACH, then, uses of mixtures containing substances manufactured or imported in quantities of >10t per year per MI and with properties and concentrations greater than the cut-off values established in CLP⁴ are required to be consistent with the operating conditions, risk management measures and exposure scenarios developed through CSA.

9.3.1.2 Intentional mixtures under CLP

In addition to the above, CLP has specific provisions for assessing the classification of mixtures. The hazard classifications are the same as those for substances under CLP and a classification is made by the formulator based on knowledge of the all of the substances and mixtures contained in the mixture for which a classification is to be made. If an ingredient in a mixture is a mixture itself then information on the substances contained in that mixture must be obtained. Once again, the process is complicated but can be summarised as follows:

- *Classification of physical hazards* - the majority of physical hazards can be determined through testing based using methods set out in Part 2 of Annex I of CLP but it is also possible to determine the classification through a calculation where sufficient data is available;
- *Classification of health and environmental hazards* - there are three main ways by which mixtures are classified for human health or environmental hazards:

⁴ For example, substances with classifications such as Acute Tox. 1-3, Aquatic Acute 1 or Aquatic Chronic 1 contained in mixtures at concentrations above 0.1% or substances with classifications of Acute Tox. 4, Skin Corr./Irrit., Aquatic Chronic 2-4 or Eye Dam./Irrit. contained in mixtures above 1%.

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- classification can be derived using data on the mixture itself, by applying the substance criteria of Annex I of CLP, for all hazards except carcinogenicity, mutagenicity and reprotoxicity, and bioaccumulation and biodegradation properties within the evaluation of “hazardous to the aquatic environment”;
- bridging principles and weight of evidence determination may be used where relevant information on the mixture itself is not available but sufficient data on similar tested mixtures and individual hazardous ingredients exist;
- where test data on the mixture or similar mixtures is not available and bridging principles cannot be applied classification may be based on calculation or on concentration thresholds for the classified substances present in the mixture. Classification of most hazard classes can be based on concentration threshold of which there are two forms: generic cut-off values⁵ and generic concentration limits⁶. Specific concentration limits (SCL) or specific cut-off values may be established for individual substances are included in Annex VI of CLP and in the C&L Inventory.

More information on the classification of mixtures can be found in the ECHA “Guidance on the Application of the CLP Criteria” <https://echa.europa.eu/guidance-documents/guidance-on-clp>

9.3.1.3 Risk control for intentional mixtures though other legislation

In addition to risk controls under REACH (described above), hazardous classifications for substances and mixtures made under CLP trigger specific pieces of parallel legislation. In addition, a substance (by itself or in a mixture) may be specifically identified in a piece of legislation and/or there may be specific requirements concerning the consideration of human health/environmental impacts for certain types of uses. This other parallel legislation can be grouped under the broad headings of:

- Occupational health and safety (OSH);
- Professional and consumer products;
- Environment; and
- Waste legislation.

OSH legislation and intentional mixtures

The following pieces of OSH legislation are triggered by certain classifications of substances and mixtures under CLP:

- **Carcinogens and mutagens Directive (CMD) - Directive 2004/37/EC on the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work** is an individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 of the OSH Framework Directive. It aims to protect workers against risks to their health and safety, including the prevention of such risks, which may arise from exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work. The definition of carcinogen and mutagen originally came from the Dangerous Substances Directive (67/548/EEC) or the Dangerous Preparations Directive (88/379/EEC). These classifications have been translated into CLP. Employers must abide by a hierarchy of measures, beginning with the obligation to reduce and replace carcinogens or mutagens where possible, prevent and reduce exposure where it is not possible to remove the substance, provide information and training to workers and carry out health surveillance in line with Member States.

⁵ The minimum concentrations for a substance to be taken into account for classification purposes. Where a classified substance is present in a concentration above the generic cut-off value it contributes to the mixture classification even if it does not directly trigger classification of the mixture.

⁶ The minimum concentrations for a substance which triggers the classification of a mixture if exceeded by the individual concentration or the sum of concentrations of relevant substances.

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- **Chemical Agents Directive (CAD)** - Council Directive 98/24/EC of 7 April 1998 on the protection of the health and safety of workers from the risks related to chemical agents at work is the fourteenth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 of the OSH Framework Directive. It outlines the minimum requirements for the protection of workers health and safety arising, or likely to arise, from the effects of chemical agents in the workplace or the use of chemical agents at work. It applies where hazardous chemical agents are present or may be present at the workplace. Indicative occupational exposure limit values (IOELVs) are set at Community level. Member States are required to introduce a national occupational exposure limit value that takes into account the IOELV. Binding biological limit values (BBLVs) may be drawn up at Community level. Member States must establish a corresponding national binding biological limit value. There are a number of obligations for employers, including carrying out an assessment of the risk to health and safety arising from the presence of chemical agents and specific protection and prevention measures. The definition of a hazardous chemical agent is where it meets the criteria for classification under the Dangerous Substances Directive (67/548/EEC) or the Dangerous Preparations Directive (88/379/EEC). These classifications have been translated into CLP.
- **Signs at work Directive** - Council Directive 92/58/EEC of 24 June 1992 on the minimum requirements for the provision of safety and/or health signs at work is the ninth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 of the OSH Framework Directive. It lays down the minimum requirements for the provision of health and safety signs at work. Employers are required to provide health and safety signs where hazards cannot be avoided or reduced. The Annexes outline the minimum requirements for health and safety signs.
- **Young workers Directive** - Council Directive 94/33/EC of 22 June 1994 on the protection of young people at work requires Member States to ensure that work by adolescents is strictly restricted and that children are prohibited from working. Employers are required to carry out an assessment of the hazards to young workers before they start work where this includes the nature, degree and duration of exposure to physical, biological and chemical agents. The classifications of chemical agents are based on the Dangerous Substances Directive (67/548/EEC) but these are now translated to those of CLP.
- **Pregnant or breastfeeding workers Directive** - Council Directive 92/85/EEC of 19 October 1992 on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding is the 10th individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 of the OSH Framework Directive (89/391/EEC). It aims to implement measures to encourage improvements in the health and safety at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or who are breastfeeding. Employers are obliged to carry out an assessment to establish the nature, degree and duration of exposure to agents, processes or working conditions under Annex I. This assessment should determine any risks to the health or safety and any possible effect on pregnancy or breastfeeding workers, and then to decide what measures should be taken. Pregnant workers are not allowed to perform duties where there may be exposure to agents or working conditions in Annex II, section A. Workers who are breastfeeding may not perform duties where there may be exposure to the agents and working conditions listed in Annex II, section B. Requirements are not limited to exposure, they also consider maternity leave, anti-natal examinations and prohibition of dismissal.

Professional and consumer legislation and intentional mixtures

A number of pieces of professional and consumer legislation require specific consideration of the hazards of mixtures in relation to uses covered by the relevant regulation, with some requiring consideration of synergistic or cumulative effects. These were reviewed in detail in JRC (2014)⁷ and can be summarised as follows:

⁷ JRC (2014): Assessment of Mixtures - Review of Regulatory Requirements and Guidance, Luxembourg, ISBN 978-92-79-38479-0, doi:10.2788/84264 - <https://eurl-ecvam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/news/assessment-mixures-report>

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- **Plant protection products and biocides** - The Plant Protection Products (Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009) outlines the rules for the authorisation of plant protection products (PPPs) in commercial form and for their placing on the market, use and control within the Community. The Biocidal Products Regulation biocides (Regulation (EU) No 528/2012) harmonises the rules for the making available on the market and the use of biocidal products and treated articles. Biocides and PPPs are generally mixtures composed of one or more active substances. Under the regulations their safety is mainly assessed based on the individual substances and the final products. Attention is given to cumulative and synergistic effects⁷;
- **Human and veterinary pharmaceuticals** - These are generally applied as mixtures. The risk assessment of human pharmaceuticals (Directive 2001/83/EC) focuses on humans, including potential interactions with other pharmaceuticals. An environmental risk assessment is also required but no attention is given to cumulative or mixture effects. Veterinary products (Directive 2001/82/EC) are assessed with emphasis on animal, human and environmental risks. The ecotoxicity assessment of veterinary mixtures is more extensive than for human pharmaceuticals, but joint occurrence with other pharmaceuticals or other pollutants is not taken into account⁷;
- **Cosmetics Products Regulation** (Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009) - Cosmetics usually consist of several substances, and their risk can be assessed on the basis of individual ingredients, combinations thereof or the whole product. Animal testing is not allowed. The anticipated exposure to the individual ingredients has to be taken into account, including possible interactions. Environmental risks are not addressed but are considered to be assessed via REACH⁷;
- **Food additives (Regulation No 1333/2008)** - Food and feed stuff can be regarded as complex mixtures. are assessed for toxicity, but the assessment of mixtures is mainly based on individual compounds. Cumulative toxic effects have to be taken into account, but how the cumulative assessment should be conducted is not specified⁷;
- **Toys Directive** (Directive 2009/48/EC) - Human risk assessment via toys focuses on individual compounds that should not be used in toys, with emphasis on the sensitivity of the target group (i.e. children). Only individual chemicals (beside nitrosamines and nitrosable compounds) are taken into account. For the toxicological properties, reference is made to REACH and the classification and labelling legislation⁷.

In addition to legislation that requires specific consideration of mixtures, other legislation is triggered by presence of certain substances or classifications under CLP. This includes:

- **Pressure Equipment Directive** (Directive 2014/68/EU) – The Directive applies to the design, manufacture and conformity assessment of pressure equipment and assemblies that have a maximum allowable pressure PS greater than 0.5 bar. It outlines the obligations of manufacturers, authorised representatives, importers and distributors. The classification of fluids are divided into two groups based on the CLP classification. Annex I sets out the essential safety requirements.
- **Restriction of the use of hazardous substances (RoHS) in electronic equipment** (Directive 2011/65/EU) - The Directive lays down the rules on the restriction of the use of hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment. It applies to all electrical and electronic equipment which falls within the categories of Annex I. it applies without prejudice to Union legislation on health and safety, REACH and particular Union waste legislation. The RoHS outlines the obligations of manufacturers, importers, authorised representatives, and distributors. Annex II lays out the substances that are restricted under Article 4(1) and their maximum concentration values. Although the substances under Annex II are restricted, there are exemptions from these restrictions in certain electrical and electronic equipment and this is outlined in Annex III. Annex IV provides a list of exemptions from the restriction for certain medical devices and monitoring and control instruments.

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- **Regulation on Import and exports** (Regulation (EU) No 649/2012) - The Regulation applies to certain hazardous chemicals that are subject to the prior informed consent under the Rotterdam Convention and certain hazardous chemicals that are banned or severely restricted within the Union or a Member State. Annex I provides the list of chemicals that are subject to the export notification procedure, the list of chemicals that qualify for PIC notification, and the list of chemicals subject to the PIC procedure. Annex V provides the list of chemicals and articles that are subject to the export ban referred to in Article 15.
- **Food contact materials and articles** (Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004) - The Regulation establishes specific requirements for the manufacture and marketing of plastic materials and articles that are intended to come into contact with food, already in contact with food, or which can be reasonably expected to come into contact with food. Only substances that are included in the Union list of authorised substances set out in Annex I can be used in the manufacture of plastic layers in plastic materials and articles, although derogations do exist. Each substance must not exceed its specific migration limit. Substances that are not listed in the Union list or the provisional list but have been approved for use cannot have a harmonised classification as CMR or be in nanoform.

Environmental legislation and intentional mixtures

Where mixtures are concerned the following environmental legislation is triggered by the classification of individual substances or specifically identified substances in a mixture rather than the mixture itself. This compliments risk management measures identified in REACH CSAs in relation to environmental risks and exposure (as described earlier):

- **Water Framework Directive (WFD)** - Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy aims to establish a framework for the protection of inland waters, transitional waters, coastal waters and groundwaters. The priorities are to: prevent further deterioration and enhance the status of aquatic ecosystems and, with regard to their water needs, terrestrial ecosystems and wetlands directly dependant on aquatic ecosystems; promote sustainable water use; enhance protection and improvement of the aquatic environment through the reduction of discharges, emissions and losses of priority substances; enhancing the progressive reduction of pollution of groundwater and preventing further pollution; and to contribute to mitigating the effects of floods and droughts.
- **Environmental quality standards Directive** - Directive 2008/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on environmental quality standards in the field of water policy, amending and subsequently repealing Council Directives 82/176/EEC, 83/513/EEC, 84/156/EEC, 84/491/EEC, 86/280/EEC and amending Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council sets out the environmental quality standards (EQS) for priority substances and certain other pollutants in line with Article 15 of the Water Framework Directive in order to achieve good surface water chemical status.
- **Drinking water Directive** - Council Directive 98/83/EC of 3 November 1998 on the quality of water intended for human consumption aims to protect human health from the adverse effects of any contamination of water that is intended for human consumption by laying out the requirements to ensure that it is clean. One of the requirements is for Member States to set quality standard values for the parameters that are set in Annex I, be that microbial or chemical. Regular monitoring is a requirement of this Directive, as is remedial action.
- **Groundwater Directive** - Directive 2006/118/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration establishes the specific measures as provided for in the Water Framework Directive in order to prevent and control groundwater pollution. It sets out the criteria for good groundwater chemical status. Member States have to consider establishing threshold values for 10 substances.

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- **Industrial emissions Directive (IED)** - Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control) lays down the rules on integrated prevention and control of pollution that arises from industrial activities. It aims to prevent, or where this is not possible, to reduce emissions to air, water and land and to prevent the generation of waste. This Directive applies to industrial activities that are referred to in Chapters II to VI, which are listed in Annex I. Annex II provides a list of polluting substances for air and water.
- **Air quality Directive** - Directive 2008/50/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2008 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe outlines the measures that should contribute to avoid, prevent or reduce harmful effects on human health or the environment. Upper and lower thresholds exist for a number of substances in Annex II.
- **VOCs Directive** - Council Directive 1999/13/EC of 11 March 1999 on the limitation of emissions of volatile organic compounds due to the use of organic solvents in certain activities and installations aims to prevent or reduce the direct and indirect effects of emissions of volatile organic compounds in the environment. It is mainly concerned with emissions to the air. In order to reduce these effects, measures and procedures are introduced for the activities that are defined in Annex I, as long as they are operated above the solvent consumption thresholds outlined in Annex IIA. Annex IIB outlines the requirements for the Reduction scheme and Annex III provides the solvent management plan.

Waste legislation and intentional mixtures

Where mixtures are concerned waste legislation does not differentiate between mixtures and substances and focusses more on the identity and properties of any individual substances, processes and sources that may pose a hazard. In this way the following waste legislation applies to constituents of mixtures and waste generating processes:

- **Waste Framework Directive** - Directive 2008/98/EC on waste lays down the measures to prevent or reduce the adverse impacts of the generation and management of waste by reducing resource use and improving efficiency of use. There are certain wastes excluded from the requirements of this Directive, such as radioactive waste. These are outlined in Article 2. The Waste Framework Directive presents a waste hierarchy which applies as a priority order in waste prevention and management legislation and policy. Requirements of this Directive are outlined for prevention of waste, recovery, reuse and recycling, and disposal. The properties of waste which render it hazardous are outlined in Annex III.
- **Directive on waste from electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE)** - Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) lays down the rules for preventing or reducing the adverse impacts if the generation and management of waste from electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE). This is to be implemented through reducing the overall impacts of resource use and improving efficiency. The categories of EEE within Annex I until 14 August 2018, then to all EEE classified within the categories set out in Annex III. This Directive provides requirements for separate collection, disposal and transport of collected WEEE and recovery targets.
- **Waste shipments Regulation** - Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2006 on shipments of waste establishes the procedures and control regimes for the shipment of waste, depending on the origin, destination and route of the shipment, the type of waste shipped and the type of treatment to be applied to the waste at its destination. The requirements of this Regulation apply to shipments of waste between Member States; imported into the Community from third countries; exported from the Community to third countries; in transit through the Community between third countries.
- Certain wastes are subject to the procedure of prior written notification and consent, these are outlined in Article 3. The notification procedure is explained in Chapter 1, which includes the contract, financial guarantee, transmission of notification and consents by the competent

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authorities of destination, dispatch and transit. This Regulation also outlines the additional provisions for interim recovery and disposal operations. The following Annexes provide lists of waste for which there are particular measures:

- Annex III - the list of wastes subject to the general information requirements laid down in Article 18.
- Annex IV - the list of wastes subject to the procedure of prior written notification and consent.
- Annex V – waste subject to the export prohibition in Article 36
- **End of life vehicles Directive (ELV)** - Directive 2000/53/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 September 2000 on end-of life vehicles lays down the measures to prevent waste from vehicles, through reuse, recycling and other forms of recovery of end of life vehicles and their components. The ELV outlines the rules for collection, treatment, reuse and recovery of end of life vehicles and their components. The minimum treatment requirements are laid out in Annex I. Article 4(2)(a) requires Member States to ensure that materials and components of vehicles put on the market after 1 July 2013 do not contain lead, mercury, cadmium or chromium VI other than in the specific cases of exemption listed in Annex II.
- **Directive on packaging and packaging waste** - European Parliament and Council Directive 94/62/EC of 20 December 1994 on packaging and packaging waste aims to harmonise national measures concerning the management of packaging and packaging waste to prevent or reduce impacts on the environment of Member States and third countries. The main priorities are to prevent the production of packaging waste through reusing, recycling and recovery of packaging. It covers all packaging placed on the market, including all packaging waste whether it is used or released at industrial, commercial, office, shop, service, household or any other level, regardless of the material used. The concentration levels of heavy metals in packaging must be controlled by Member States in accordance with Article 11.
- **Waste batteries and accumulators** - Directive 2006/66/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 September 2006 on batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators and repealing Directive 91/157/EEC lays down the rules for the placing on the market of batteries and accumulators, including the prohibition of the placing on the market of those containing hazardous substances. It also includes specific rules for the collection, treatment, recycling and disposal of waste batteries and accumulators. This Directive applies to all types of battery and accumulator unless they are used in equipment connected to the protection of Member States' essential security interests, arms, munitions and war material, unless not intended for specific military purposes, or equipment designed to be sent into space. Batteries and accumulators cannot contain more than the specific concentration of certain metals as outlined in Article 4

9.3.2 Unintentional and coincidental mixtures

In contrast to the intentional mixtures that are marketed as products, managing the risks of unintentional and coincidental mixtures is much more challenging.

As identified in Section 1 unintentional mixtures are mixtures originating from a single source as result of discharges to the environment during the production, transport, use or disposal of goods, often contain a mixture of chemical substances. The composition can either be known (for example an effluent) or it can be unknown. Coincidental mixtures are mixtures of chemicals originating from multiple sources and through multiple pathways. They relate to multiple substances from multiple and varying sources. Their composition is unknown and can vary in both space and time.

Owing to the complexities of substance identity and variations including in composition, sources, pathways, receiving environment and individuals, there are relatively few legislative instruments that address or seek to address the assessment of effects. Those that have been identified in the

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Commission's communication on the combination effects of chemicals (COM, 2012)⁸ and JRC (2014)⁹ are briefly described in the sections below.

Considering the scope of legislation more generally, JRC's 2014 *Review of Regulatory Requirements and Guidance*⁹ concludes that "while many pieces of EU legislation are in place to protect humans and the environment against adverse effects of chemicals including mixtures, in many cases it remains unclear how this is to be carried out and only few explicitly consider (real life) exposure to mixtures. In cases where mixtures are considered, the assessment is frequently limited to some well-known components. Several mathematical models and approaches have been developed to assess the toxicity of mixtures, but their routine application is hampered by considerable information gaps".

From the point of view of bio-monitoring and the HBM4EU project, the Commission's 2012 communication⁸ identifies that "there is a need to better understand human and environmental exposures, both through the use of monitoring and modelling". The potential role of monitoring programmes in the identification of priority mixtures is also highlighted in a more recent (2014) German Federal Environment Agency report¹⁰. This identifies that data could be used not only to detect single substances for potential prioritisation but could also be analysed to identify whether certain substances occur in combination or are correlated in concentration to each other. The report identifies that this, in turn, would help to nominate priority mixtures.

9.3.2.1 REACH Regulation (No 1907/2006)

All chemical substances manufactured or imported in quantities of >1t per year per manufacturer/importer (MI) must be registered under REACH. COM (2012) identifies that in the context of REACH guidance has been developed concerning the assessment of multiple sources of exposure to a single substance and in specific cases to the assessment of several closely related and similarly acting substances such as different salts of the same metal or a number of closely related derivatives of organic substances (see for example ECHA, 2016¹¹). Whilst this gives some scope to assess known combinations that may have adverse effects, it does not address wider issues associated with wider combinations of chemical substances.

9.3.2.2 OSH legislation

The Chemical Agents Directive (CAD) ([Directive 98/24/EC](#)) outlines the minimum requirements for the protection of workers health and safety arising, or likely to arise, from the effects of chemical agents in the workplace or the use of chemical agents at work. There are a number of obligations for employers, including carrying out an assessment of the risk to health and safety arising from the presence of chemical agents and specific protection and prevention measures. The Directive specifies maximum levels for individual substances and also explicitly refers to chemical agents in combination including both unintentional and coincidental mixtures.

9.3.2.3 Professional and consumer legislation

Food contaminants and food contact materials - JRC (2014) identifies that, with the exception of dioxins and dioxin-like compounds, [Regulation 315/93/EEC](#) on contaminants in food does not

⁸ European Commission (2012): Communication from the Commission to the Council: The combination effects of chemicals – Chemical mixtures, COM(2012) 252 final, Brussels, 31.5.2012. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52012DC0252>

⁹ JRC (2014): Assessment of Mixtures - Review of Regulatory Requirements and Guidance, Luxembourg, ISBN 978-92-79-38479-0, doi:10.2788/84264 - <https://eurl-ecvam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/news/assessment-mixtures-report>

¹⁰ UBA (2014): Mixtures in the Environment – Development of Assessment Strategies for the Regulation of Chemicals under REACH. https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/378/publikationen/texte_65_2014_aust_hassold_mixtures_in_the_environment.pdf

¹¹ http://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13632/information_requirements_part_e_en.pdf

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take mixture toxicity or combination effects. [Regulation 1935/2004/EC on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food](#) considers cumulative effects but these are undefined and mixture toxicity is not considered.

Pesticide residues in food - [Regulation 396/2005/EC on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin](#) acknowledges the need for cumulative and mixture toxicity assessment when establishing MRLs. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has developed approaches for assessing combined exposure to multiple pesticides and contaminants in humans and multiple pesticides in bees. It is now developing and consulting on approaches to the harmonisation of risks to humans and the environment from multiple chemicals in the food chain (see <http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/chemical-mixtures>)

9.3.2.4 Environmental legislation

Aquatic environment – [The Water Framework Directive \(WFD\) 2000/60/EC](#) establishes a framework for Community action in the field of water policy with the aim of achieving ‘good ecological status’ of waterbodies across the community. Although it does not explicitly identify combination effects of chemicals, as is identified in COM (2012), the requirement for water bodies to achieve good ecological status as well as good chemical status requires a focus not only on the concentrations of individual chemicals but also on their effects on the aquatic environment in combination.

Marine environment - [Marine Strategy Framework Directive 2008/56/EC](#) establishes a framework to achieve good environmental status in the marine environment by 2020. As identified by COM (2012), the Directive identifies that risk assessment should also consider cumulative and mixture effects. However, how this should be achieved is not specified.

Industrial emissions - [Directive 2010/75/EU on industrial emissions](#) lays down the rules on integrated prevention and control of pollution from industrial activities. It aims to prevent, or where this is not possible, to reduce emissions to air, water and land and to prevent the generation of waste. With the exception of dioxins and furans, however, mixture and combination effects are not considered.

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) – the [EIA Directive 2011/92/EU](#) sets out requirements for the environmental impact assessment of large scale public and private projects. There is a requirement to consider and estimate emissions of pollutants and assess cumulative effects of impacts. Chemical mixture toxicity is not, however, specifically addressed.

9.3.2.5 Further information

2011 Opinion of the European Commission’s non-food scientific committees (SCCS, SCHER and SCENIHR) -

http://ec.europa.eu/health/scientific_committees/environmental_risks/docs/scher_o_155.pdf

2009 Report Commissioned by DG Environment: *State of the Art Report on Mixture Toxicity* -

http://ec.europa.eu/environment/chemicals/effects/pdf/report_mixture_toxicity.pdf

DG Environment webpage on combination effects of chemicals -

http://ec.europa.eu/environment/chemicals/effects/effects_en.htm

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10 Annex 2 - Longlist of statements from the literature (see section 5.1) and from apparent discourse in HJMP interactions.

Statements from literature on expert roles in science-policy interface	
1	As an expert, it is my duty to maintain continuous dialogue with policymakers.
2	As an expert, it is my responsibility to inform policymakers about all possible policy options and their potential consequences.
3	As an expert, it is my task to recommend the policy option that I consider best.
4	I try to use my scientific knowledge to actively direct policy.
5	In my opinion, science should be limited to systematic knowledge production.
6	I think there should be strict separation between scientists who do research and policymakers who build policy on that research.
7	When scientific knowledge is inconclusive, I think policymakers have the task of dealing with the resulting uncertainty.
8	I think that scientific research should contribute to solving societal problems.
9	My only involvement in politics is to address specific questions posed by policymakers.
10	In addition to scientific knowledge, I preferably incorporate my personal values in my policy advice.
11	I think policy makers are best supported when experts are transparent about their personal preferences with regard to the policy alternatives and the motivation for these preferences.
12	I think that public anxiety is a good motivation for policy action, even when there is no scientific explanation for the anxiety.
13	If the health and environmental impacts of a project involving environmental health risks were highly uncertain, I would advise precautionary measures to protect public health and the environment.
14	I believe the uncertainties of environmental health risks warrant significant investment in additional research.
15	I believe the uncertainties of environmental health risks warrant significant investment in precautionary measures.
16	In my opinion, knowledge of the general public is of less value to policymakers than expert knowledge.
17	I expect future technological innovations to reduce the negative effects of contaminants on health and the environment.
18	I think new policies on environment health risks should be based entirely on the best available scientific knowledge.
19	I believe the risks and uncertainties of environmental health risks require monitoring but there is currently no need for additional regulatory measures.
20	As an expert, I think I should cooperate with stakeholders in assessing environmental health risks.
21	I feel personally motivated to initiate stakeholder cooperation in my research on environment health risks.
22	I expect the government to coordinate the governance process on environmental health risks.
23	I think that possible health problems concerning environmental risks are best managed by legislation and regulation.
24	In my opinion, public health and environmental risk problems are too complex for only evidence-based policy.
25	As an expert, I should take the perspectives of the general public into account in my research.
26	In giving policy advice, I think experts should be completely open about the methods they use and assumptions they make.
27	I think I should inform policy makers about the science underlying my policy advice.

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- 28 My views on the environmental health risks tend to differ from those of my colleagues.
- 29 I generally agree with current policies on environmental health risks.
- 30 I am very interested in the political debate surrounding my research.
- 31 I think the primary task of a scientist is to publish in peer-reviewed scientific journals.
- 32 I primarily work in science because I like the intellectual challenge.
- 33 I think scientists should be humble about the role of science in solving societal problems.
- 34 I think scientists should 'speak truth to power' in their policy advice.
- 35 I think that scientific output should be assessed by an extended peer community of all who are affected by the issue.
- 36 I think that differences of opinion among experts should be made explicit when giving policy advice.
- 37 Just as NGOs and industry do, I think scientists should actively approach politicians to present their points of view on mixtures.
- 38 I think policy makers are best served when experts strive for consensus in their policy advice.

Statements from Myth of Nature and Cultural Theory pertaining to risk governance

- 39 Nature is - within limits - robust to changes and will find a new equilibrium
- 40 Nature is sensitive to small changes which can bring natural systems to collapse
- 41 Nature is benign and has an unlimited capacity to find its way to a new equilibrium
- 42 Nature is unpredictable with random happenings that cannot be controlled or predicted
- 43 As an expert, I should not participate in civil action groups
- 44 Important questions about acceptability of health risks should not be left to experts but to the public
- 45 Important questions about acceptability of health risks should not be left to experts but to policy makers
- 45 Important questions about acceptability of health risks should not be left to experts but to policy makers

Statements adopted from actual discourse on dealing with mixtures (paraphrased)

- 46 Excessive exposures to mixtures of chemicals are best managed by personal (lifestyle) choices
- 47 Excessive exposures to mixtures of chemicals are best managed by regulation within my DG (e.g. Sante, Environment, Employment, Growth or their national equivalents)
- 48 Excessive exposures to mixtures of chemicals can only be managed by regulation jointly across different DGs
- 49 To reduce excessive exposure to mixtures, the biggest contributors to these risks should be regulated first and their contributions reduced
- 50 To reduce excessive exposure to mixtures, all contributors to these risks should be regulated simultaneously and their contributions proportionally reduced
- 51 To reduce excessive exposure to mixtures, the contributors that are cheapest to regulate and reduce should be tackled first
- 52 To reduce excessive exposure to mixtures, the contributions from products/applications with the least favorable benefit/risk ratio should be regulated and reduced first
- 53 To reduce excessive exposure to mixtures, involuntary exposures should be regulated first, since citizens have no influence on them
- 54 To reduce excessive exposure to mixtures, reduction of voluntary exposures by citizens is the most effective strategy
- 55 To reduce excessive exposure to mixtures, intentional mixtures should be first targeted
- 56 To reduce excessive exposure to mixtures, mixtures originating from a single source should be first targeted
- 57 Technological improvements and innovations will automatically reduce exposure and body burdens to mixtures of chemicals
- 58 New technologies will lead to new exposures of unknown chemicals, further increasing our body burdens to mixtures of chemicals

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59	Current legislation is adequate to reduce excessive exposures to mixtures through targeting intentional mixtures
60	Current legislation is adequate to reduce excessive exposures to mixtures through targeting unintentional mixtures from a single source
61	Current legislation is adequate to reduce excessive exposures to mixtures through targeting coincidental mixtures from multiple sources and through multiple pathways
62	Mixture risk assessment and management needs to be explicitly addressed in relevant regulations prior to any effective mixture risk management to take place
63	Mixture risk assessment is sufficiently developed to start implementation in risk management, even though it is not yet explicitly addressed in regulations
64	Expert committees should explicitly address relevant mixture information, even where this is not required by regulations
65	Mixture risk assessment methodology is currently not sufficiently mature to be incorporated in the regulatory context
66	Application of standard safety/assessment factors are sufficiently conservative to incorporate potential mixture effects
67	Additional safety/assessment factors are needed to incorporate potential mixture effects
68	Policy makers are responsible to reduce the exposure to mixtures, as industry can only be held responsible for the safety of their products, regardless of any mixture contribution
69	If safer substitutes are available, irrespective of the risks, chemicals should be replaced by these safer substitutes to reduce mixture risks
70	Unintentional and coincidental mixtures are impossible to regulate, because each person is exposed to different mixtures every day

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